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● **A species name which should not “survive” one more day: *Neolucanus horizontalis* Xin, Zhong & Qi, 2025, a junior synonym of *N. yemaoi* Wang & He, 2024 (Coleoptera: Lucanidae)**

Cheng-Bin WANG¹ & Tian-Long HE^{2*}

¹Engineering Research Center for Forest and Grassland Disaster Prevention and Reduction, Mianyang Normal University, Mianyang 621000, Sichuan Province, China; <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-7913-8779>; entomologist@qq.com

²Donghuaxincheng, Wangfenggang, Xiejiaji District, Huainan 232046, Anhui Province, China; <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-7301-5105>; htl1988@qq.com

*Corresponding author

Abstract: *Neolucanus horizontalis* Xin, Zhong & Qi, 2025, which was published today with detailed description and clear illustrations, is sufficient to be confirm as one recently described as *N. yemaoi* Wang & He, 2024, making *N. horizontalis* a junior synonym of *N. yemaoi*.

Keywords: China, Odontolabini, synonymy, taxonomy

● **一个不该多“存活”一天的物种名：平颧圆翅锹为叶茂圆翅锹之次异名（鞘翅目：锹甲科）**

王成斌¹ & 贺天龙^{2*}

¹森林与草原防灾减灾工程研究中心，绵阳师范学院，绵阳 621000，四川省，中国

²东华鑫城，望峰岗，谢家集区，淮南 232046，安徽省，中国

*通讯作者

摘要：今日发表的平颧圆翅锹 *Neolucanus horizontalis* Xin, Zhong & Qi, 2025，附有详细的描述与清晰的图版，足以证实其即最近描述的叶茂圆翅锹 *N. yemaoi* Wang & He, 2024，这也使得前者成为叶茂圆翅锹之次异名。

关键词：中国，奥锹族，同义，分类

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● Introduction

On January 17th, 2025, just today, Xin *et al.* (2025) published their stag beetle species, namely *Neolucanus horizontalis* Xin, Zhong & Qi, 2025, from Yunnan Province of China, based on only 2 males. However, the identical species has already been described by Wang & He (2024) under the name of *Neolucanus yemaoi* Wang & He, 2024 on December 4th, 2024, based on 6 males and 6 females. Very soon after, on December 30th, 2024, Huang & Chen (2024) proposed the diagnosis of this species based on a large series of specimens. In this paper, we synonymise *N. horizontalis* with *N. yemaoi*.

From the textual information of Xin *et al.* (2025), we can know that the acceptance date for their manuscript is December 3rd, 2024, and through Chinese social media, the authors were well aware that this species had already been published, despite being able to replace the species name after accepting, they knowingly published the same species as a new again. As a taxonomical veteran, we will all encounter situations in our lifetimes where a new species we are describing is published by someone else first. Do we all have to go and publish this kind of newly published species under another name again?

● Taxonomy

Neolucanus yemaoi Wang & He, 2024 叶茂圆翅锹

Fig. 1

Wang & He 2024: 155, Figs 1, 2A–F, 3A–C, 4A–H, 5A–D, 6A–C, 7C (description; illustrations; **type locality**: “CHINA, Yunnan: Honghe Prefecture, Pingbian County, Daweishan National Nature Reserve [大围山国家级自然保护区], 2090 m”); Huang & Chen 2024: 11, figs. 7–9, 11–13, 17 (characters; illustrations; remarks).

Synonymy. *Neolucanus horizontalis* Xin, Zhong & Qi in Xin, Zhong, Guo, Zhang, Qi & Wu, 2025: 346, Figs 1A, B, 2A, B, 3E–H, 4A–D, 5A–H, 6A, B, E, F, I, J, 7A, B (description; illustrations; **type locality**: “China, Yunnan Province, Honghe Prefecture, Lvchun County, Pinghe Town, 22°49′10″N, 102°31′26″E, 8.VI.2024, 1316m”). **syn. nov.**

Distribution. China (Yunnan).

FIGURE 1. Dorsal habitus of the largest male paratype (A) and the holotype (C) of *Neolucanus yemaoi* Wang & He, 2024, and the holotype (B) of *Neolucanus horizontalis* Xin, Zhong & Qi, 2025 **syn. nov.**

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● Additional information

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